

Temple of Hatshepsut at Deir el-Bahri

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Entry tags: Religious Complex, Archaeological monument, Religious Place, Solar cult, Egyptian Religions, Deir el-Bahari, Cult of Hathor, Cult of Amun, Royal cult, Religious Group, Ancient Egypt, Temple of Hatshepsut, Temple, Temenos

The temple of queen Hatshepsut at Deir el-Bahari was a terraced ancient Egyptian temple of millions of years. It was dedicated to the cult of Amun, as well as Hathor and Anubis, Hatshepsut herself and her father Thutmose I also had their chapels here. Its construction started in the 7th year of the reign of Thutmose III and continued through all her life. It was situated in the valley at the foot of the mountain. The whole complex consisted of the Valley Temple, 1km-long processional alley and the main temple. The Hathor Shrine was a separate element, with its own architectural arrangement and a priest. The temple was oriented to the east, towards the 8th pylon in Karnak. It has undergone many architectural changes, although some elements have never been finished. Its architect was Senenmut, one of the queen's most trusted officials. In the late years of the reign of Thutmose III, the temple lost importance in favour of his temple built right next to it, on the south side. The decoration of the temple suffered many alterations, Thutmose III removed figures of the queen and her royal protocol or replaced them with those of his father, Thutmose II. During the Amarna period, almost all representations of gods and gods' barks were chiselled out. In the post-Amarna times, most of the gods' depictions were restored. In the Third Intermediate Period, the serious earthquake destroyed the Upper Terrace and the temple space began to be used as a graveyard for high officials and their families. During the Graeco-Roman period, the parts of the temple not damaged by the earthquake served as a place of the cult of Amenhotep son of Hapu and Imhotep, and a sanatory.

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 348 CE

Region: Deir el-Bahari

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Egypt, Egypt, Deir el-Bahari, el-Asasif

This entry focuses on the 11th dynasty temple of Mentuhotep II, which is located in the valley of Deir el-Bahari, next to the 18th dynasty mortuary temples of Hatshepsut and Thutmosis III .

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Edouard Naville. The Temple of Deir el-Bahari: its plan, its founders, and its first explorers, Introductory Memoir. London 1894

- Source 2: Marcelle Werbrouck. Le temple d'Hatshepsout à Deir el Bahari. Brüssel: Fondation égyptologique Reine Élisabeth 1949
- Source 3: Jadwiga Iwaszczuk. Sacred Landscape of Thebes During the Reign of Hatshepsut. Royal Construction Projects. Volume 1. Topography of the West Bank, Warsaw 2016

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://debprojects.uw.edu.pl/en>
 - Source 1 Description: The webpage of the Polish-Egyptian Archaeological and Conservation Mission at the Temple of Hatshepsut at Deir el-Bahari
 - Source 2 URL: https://www.maat-ka-ra.de/english/start_e.htm
 - Source 2 Description: Useful guide
- Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Type of excavation:

– Illicit

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Scientific

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Pre-modern

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1855

Notes: John Green

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1893–1899, 1903–1906

Notes: Edouard Naville (Egypt Exploration Fund)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1925–1944

Notes: Emile Baraize

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1931–1932

Notes: Walter Hausner

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1993–1999

Notes: Franciszek Pawlicki (Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology of the University of Warsaw)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 2020 till today

Notes: Patryk Chudzik (Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology of the University of Warsaw)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1817

Notes: Giovanni Battista Belzoni and Henry William Beechey

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1855

Notes: Auguste Mariette, E. Brune

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1911–1931

Notes: Herbert Eustis Winlock (Metropolitan Museum of Art)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1909–1910

Notes: Howard Carter, The Earl of Carnarvon

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1934

Notes: Ambrose Lansing

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1961-1967

Notes: Leszek Dąbrowski (Research Centre in Cairo of the University of Warsaw)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1968-1988

Notes: Zygmunt Wysocki (Ateliers for Conservation of Cultural Property)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Year range: 1999-2019

Notes: Zbigniew E. Szafrński (Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology of the University of Warsaw)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: The Polish-Egyptian Archaeological and Conservation Mission at the Temple of Hatshepsut at Deir el-Bahari (since 1961)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: El-Qurn

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Cave

Notes: Hathor Shrine was carved in the cave. Hathor is often represented as coming out the mountain.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Plantings

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: The temple is situated in the necropolis, on the west bank of the Nile. The rural area is removed about 1 km from the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: The processional alley connects the temple with the rural area.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ A single structure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

Notes: Two trees were planted in front of the main door to the temenos, two other trees decorated the Lower Portico, T-shape ponds planted with papyrus plants were dug in front of the Lower Ramp.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The temple temenos is a single structure containing several structures inside. The Valley Temple was planned as an isolated element, however, it remained unfinished. It was separated from the main temple by a processional alley. The Hathor Shrine was also an independent structure with its own ramp. It was rebuilt several

times during the reign of Hatshepsut as well as the rest of the temple of the queen.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ A group of features:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: Although the temple is not a part of a larger place, it is included into the processional route consisting of several temples built not only during the reign of Hatshepsut but also by her predecessors, a.o. Mentuhotep II and Amenhotep I.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: As any of Egyptian temples, it served for a cult of gods, the king and in this case, also the royal family to some extent.

Notes: Regular believers had no access to the temple. On some occasions, it was probably open to the elite members who also participated in the cult and financed it, supporting its construction and giving donations, offerings etc.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– No

Notes: The general shape of the temple is finished, but some parts were not fully constructed (e.g. Valley temple, Northern Colonnade). The decoration in some places was unfinished (e.g. western niche of the Altar Court).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The reconstruction of the temple has been carried out since the beginning of the 20th century.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Gods: Amun/Amun-Ra, Hathor, Anubis, Ennead; kings: Hatshepsut and her father - Thutmose I; during the reign of Thutmose III, names of Hatshepsut were replaced with those of father of Thutmose III - Thutmose II. Also queen Ahmose mother of Hatshepsut participated in the cult.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Amun-Ra, Hathor, king

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: Royal family members, and especially women belonging to the royal family: queen Ahmes - mother of Hatshepsut, Nefrure - sister of Hatshepsut and Senseneb - mother of Thutmose I, participated in the cult. They were represented in the Main Sanctuary of Amun, the Upper Shrine of Anubis and on the walls of the Upper Courtyard. They also took part in the festival processions.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The temple was built during the lifetime of Hatshepsut. But she was not the only one who financed the construction of the temple, several high-rank officials were also involved.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Corvee labourers

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: All workers and their supervisors were men. It was a complicated project, workers were divided into two teams, some of them were specialists, e.g. stonemasons, sculptors, painters etc. Unqualified workers were used for the transport of stone material and other types of work that did not require special skills. A big group of scribes was also involved in the process of the construction of the temple.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Notes: The temple was funded by Hatshepsut. The construction of temples was her royal duty. Amun claimed that he knew that she would build the temple while she was in the nest, i.e. she was a young child not chosen yet to be a king.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Notes: Although the birth cycle of Hatshepsut was the main theme of decoration of one of the porticos, the so-called Birth Portico.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: The functioning of the temple was motivated by keeping the order of the world. The king himself and the performance of the cult in a proper way were a guarantee of this order called Maat. The king in return received all important features of his kingship: life, prosperity, stabilisation and many more.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 28717

Notes: Only the main temple, without the Valley Temple and the processional alley.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 24.5

Notes: Main temple

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 28717

Notes: Only the main temple, without the Valley Temple and the processional alley.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 24.5

Notes: Main temple

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Earth

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Sand

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Clay

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Wood

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Any wooden elements of architecture are unpreserved.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The primary construction material was limestone sourced locally, but the statues, which decorated the temple, were made of diorite, granite, indurate limestone, sandstone etc. transported here from different parts of Egypt.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

Notes: Only the local limestone comes from the quarries located nearby, while other kinds of stones were imported here.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Some pigments were human-made, as well as mortar, all based on natural materials.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Kheker-frieze, cryptogramme frieze

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the decoration was hidden from view because access to the temple was limited. Some decorated parts were carved on the surface inside the wall (royal cartouches engraved on the inner faces of blocks placed in the wall). Representations of Senenmut were invisible: they were placed behind the doors. Most of the temple decoration was almost invisible in the dark rooms of the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: The decoration in the niches were hidden behind the wooden doors, so it was temporary uncovered. The representations of the architect of the temple, Senenmut, were hidden behind the door, so they might be visible from inside only when the doors were closed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: We can only assume their presence. In the Bark Shrine of the Hathor Shrine, there are the mountings of the statue. The statue's skids were also found there. From Deir el-Bahari comes the head of a statue of a cow (The British Museum EA42179). The existence of the statue of Amun one can guess based on the presence of the ebony naos decorated with the representation of the daily ritual on the god's statue.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Hatshepsut's statues in great number were elements of the decoration of the temple. There were sphinxes, Osiride statues, kneeling, seated and striding statues. The representations of the statues of the royal family suggest that they, at least temporarily, were present in the temple during the festivals. Some private statues were also found in the temple area.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Sphinxes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Reliefs representing the Puntic and Nubian landscape

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Type

–Secco

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

–Other [specify]: Some paints were applied directly on the stone.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: All reliefs in the temple were covered with paintings. Some parts of the decoration were only painted, especially details were treated this way. In the places hidden from view, some fragments were only painted and not carved, e.g. dado-frieze in some niches.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Reliefs representing the Puntic and Nubian landscape

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: The vertical panels with the Horus name of Hatshepsut carved on the outer face of the south retaining wall of the Middle Terrace can be called ornamental.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The historical inscription was decorated once on the south wall of the Obelisks Portico. The transport of the obelisks from Assuan depicted on the west wall of the Obelisks Portico and the Punt expedition carved on walls of the Punt Portico can be regarded as historical events.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: There are dedicatory inscriptions carved in different parts of the temple, a.o. on architraves, columns and frames of the niches in the Upper Courtyard, on the west wall of the Courtyard of the Royal Cult Complex, on the door jambs of many rooms, on columns in the Lower Anubis Shrine and Hathor Shrine, on south and north walls of the Second Hypostyle Hall of the Hathor Shrine etc.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Royal protocol

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

– Other [specify]: Inscriptions describing rituals

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Friezes (dado-frieze, cryptogramme frieze, kheker-frieze, geometric frieze), torus moulds, corniches, false doors, decorated balustrades

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Humans

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Friezes, royal protocol

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 162 CE

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Notes: There are two chapels of the kings: Chapel of Hatshepsut and Chapel of Thutmose I. When the decoration was being made, Thutmose I was already dead. In some niches, the figure of Thutmose II,

also passed away at that time, was carved.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: In addition to deities, deceased rulers were also the object of worship.

For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

Notes: The king as an office and the kingship were more important than the human being. The king was a god as a successor of Horus.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Amun/Amun-Ra is considered to be a supreme high god in the temple, however, in some parts of the temple other gods are more important, e.g. in the Hathor Shrine, it is Hathor who is the host of the place and in the Lower and Upper Anubis Shrines, Anubis is the main figure.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Notes: Anubis who is venerated in two chapels (Lower and Upper Shrines of Anubis) may be considered as chthonic divinity.

Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– I don't know

Notes: Hatshepsut is worshipped in the temple but her relationship with Amun is not unequivocal. She was considered as Amun's daughter in the birth cycle represented in the Birth Portico, her ka was a member of Ennead in the south chapel of the Statue Room. How far the king during the reign of Hatshepsut can be identified with a god is not recognised.

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– I don't know

Notes: In the temple, gods are represented as recipients of rituals and offerings and donators of the most important features of the kingship (life, stability, prosperity, sed festivals etc) who keep the world in balance by introducing Maat. Goodness as the quality was not crucial and as such was not described in temple inscriptions. Amun is pleasant to queen Ahmes when he appears to her in the form of Thutmose I.

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: None

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

Notes: There are no proofs of divine interventions and communication with gods inside the temple. The king is, of course, represented bringing offerings and performing rituals, and it was taking place in front of gods' statues. In the inscriptions, the king offers to the god and the god answers to the king. The interactions between the king and the god do not necessary had taken place in the temple. The most famous relation of queen Ahmes with Amun and the begetting of queen Hatshepsut is depicted on the walls of the Birth Portico, but the scene happened in the palace.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: During the Graeco-Roman times, the temple served as a place of the cult of Amenhotep son of Hapu and Imhotep and sanatory. Amenhotep son of Hapu was venerated as one who procured miraculous healings and delivered oracles. Sick people, who visited the temple with written requests for healing, after the night spent in the temple were healed and left written reports from the course of the healing.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Oracles took place in the Graeco-Roman period.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: During the Pharaonic times.

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

Notes: Theoretically, the king was the only performer of rituals in the temple. In fact, the priests acted on his behalf.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Notes: The king as an akh-spirit had the power to move between his tomb and the temple through the false door. His ka participated in rituals, as it is represented in the south chapel of the Statue Room. But this happened every day for eternity and not previously.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: E.g. Hathor is represented as a cow, Anubis is depicted as a jackal etc.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Some gods were represented as half human and half animals, e.g. Hathor, Anubis etc.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: They had the same power as other gods regardless of their actual form.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: The cult statues were placed in chapels, and access to them was restricted to wab-priests and the king. The statue of Hathor, according to reliefs in her shrine, was visible in the procession during her festival.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: The cult statues were invisible to most of the society. The statue of Amun was hidden inside the naos placed on the god's bark during the festivals processions. The name of Amun means "the hidden one".

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– No

Notes: The visitors left some inscriptions on the walls of the temple but nothing can be said about the visitors' relations with gods. There are also ostraca with offering lists, some of the ostraca mention also the beauty of the temple.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The animal offerings were performed in the temple.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: food offerings, drink offerings, oils, textiles, incense etc.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ By all the community

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: king and priests on his behalf

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: most of the figures and titulary of Hatshepsut as well as some figures of her daughter Nefrure were erased, some of them were replaced with offering tables, figures of other kings (mainly Thutmose II), inscriptions or standards in the case of Hatshepsut's representations and queen Ahmose in case of Nefrure; part of the decoration with the representations of gods and a portable bark of Amun was chiseled out during the Amarna period and restored during the post-Amarna period

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimages were not the reason for the construction of the temple but they can be seen as the main reason for the establishment of the place during the Graeco-Roman period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– No

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

↳ Death

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Haeling

Notes: In the Graeco-Roman times.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Priests

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Local elites

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Private contributions

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Other

– Other [specify]: King

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Wab-priests and the king were allowed to enter all places in the temple, it is not certain if the elite could participate in the parts of the festivals performed on the festival courtyard (Upper Courtyard)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Some festivals were celebrated every year (i.e. Beautiful Feast of Djoser-djeseru, Hathor Festival, New Year Festival). The festival calendar is not preserved but it is probable that more feasts were held in the temple. There were also festivals on the occasion of some important events (e.g. transport of obelisks from Assuan or come back from the Punt expedition).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Elites

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The kings (Hatshepsut and Thutmose III) were the performers of every festival taken place in the temple, the staff of the temple and people in the temple service were also present.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: The processional statues of the royal family were carried during the festivals processions. The bark of Amun with the statue of the god hidden in a naos visited the place every year, during the Beautiful Festival of Djoser-djeseru and the Hathor Festival. Hathor statue on skids was also transported during the Hathor Festival.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
– number: Impossible to determine.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:
Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

↳ Divination through human communication:
– Yes

↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

– Yes

Notes: In dreams.

↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:

– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– No

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– No

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– No

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Dream

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– Yes

Notes: In the Graeco-Roman times.

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– Yes

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Impossible to determine.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: The everyday service was performed in the temple, probably the rituals had taken place three time a day. There were also rituals connected with festivals.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: All rituals participants had to be purified.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: Some people from the personnel bear titles which connect them especially with this temple (i.e. the First Priest of Amun in Djoser-djeseru).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: There were four phyles (i.e. groups of priests) changing on the yearly basis.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: There was a hierarchy among the priests but they probably belonged to the middle class of Egyptian society. Some people involved in the construction of the temple and cult were the high-rang officials, a.o. Senenmut, the architect of the temple, and Hapuseneb, the First Priest of Amun in Karnak.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them certainly are, e.g. the First Priest of Amun Senenu, we cannot be sure if the regular staff was dedicated to the place for life.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Building dipinti, and notes from the time of the walls decoration and its restoration, were painted on the walls' surface.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1473 BCE - 800 BCE

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions were carved on the walls of the temple, mainly in raised, sometimes in sunken relief.

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Nothing from temple archives survived. On the other hand, the inscriptions were carved on the walls of the temple.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: The scenes representing the foundation of the temple are depicted in the Obelisks Portico.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: It seems that the main role of the priests was to repeat the texts during the recitations. On the other hand, the person who made an iconographical programme of the temple used the patterns known from other temples and was free to make a new arrangement of the texts and iconography.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

Notes: They are an integral part of the decoration.

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Notes: They are part of the decoration.

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

Notes: Dedicatory inscriptions are placed in different parts of the temple. They decorate the door jambs of rooms and niches, and some of them are elements of walls decoration.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

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